

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING CHILDREN TO ENGLISH WITH EARLY CHILDHOOD WITH THE HELP OF GAME LEARNING METHODS

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Annotation:

This article is about the introduction of gaming technologies in teaching preschool children the basics of a foreign (English) language. The aim of this research to show the benefits of using games in teaching a foreign language as well as several children's games for learning English.

Key words: *learning a foreign (English) language, preschool age, teaching methods and ways of teaching English, the advantage of the game, game in the concept of children, game learning technologies.*

INTRODUCTION

Foreign languages are becoming more and more popular and preferred in everyday life. It is useful to know many languages, and I want to mention that one of the common languages of international communication is English. Learning English today has become popular among modern society. And, in my opinion, this is correct! A foreign language has become a compulsory subject of instruction not only in schools, but also in many additional preschool institutions. Preschool age, from the point of view of psychology and pedagogy, is the best time to start learning a foreign language. Based on this, we can conclude that the sooner you start learning a foreign language,

the more efficiently, faster and easier it will be given to him, and the more languages he can calmly in the future. But such young students need a special approach and special techniques. But how to teach a baby who cannot read, write, and sometimes even speak? We will try to answer these questions in this article.

For children of preschool age, the game is of exceptional importance: the game for them is study, the game for them is work, the game for them is a serious form of learning.

BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

The fact is that these cute creatures are ready to do a variety of things with pleasure, but only those that they like. Teaching children is not as easy as it seems. Despite the fact that the teacher of kids 2-5 years old does not have to teach them complex tense coordination, incorrect lags, the use of gerunds - he must know a huge number of effective ways to keep their attention and instill interest in English.

Children who learn foreign languages at preschool age develop better cognitive abilities, they master reading earlier, they are able to learn the language flexibly and at an abstract level, which is manifested in judgments about the grammar of the language, in understanding the play on words.

Language learning during this period gives better results, because it is carried out in a sensitive period of child development: the plasticity of the natural mechanism of language acquisition, imitation abilities, natural curiosity and the need to learn new things contribute to the development of children's intellectual, speech and emotional abilities. (Vereshchagina I.N., Negnevitskaya E.I., Izhogina T.I., Eremina O.P., Galskova N.D., Grigoryeva E.I., Safonova V.V. Mayer A.A., Luran S ., Verbovskaya M.I., Shishkova I.A., Bonk N.A., Wenger L.A., Vygotsky L.S., Galperin P.Ya., Leontiev A.A., Amonashvili Sh.A. and etc.). The possibilities of preschool age in mastering a foreign language are truly unique: “A

child learns in a few months to speak a foreign language in a way that he cannot learn in a few years” (K.D. Ushinsky).

METHODOLOGY

Early teaching of a foreign language to preschoolers provides an opportunity for a flexible transition to in-depth study of it in elementary school, and allows you to maintain a positive motivation for studying this subject in the future.

In order to effectively solve the indicated problem, various forms and methods are used in practical work with children, aimed at the formation of mental operations, speech activity, and the desire for knowledge of the surrounding reality. A special place is occupied by the game, which is a way of familiarizing with the world of adults, a way of learning.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

There are many modern methods of teaching English, but only a few of them are really effective.

The main method used in kindergarten, children of preschool and school age, is the game method, knowledge of language features and application in practice.

The most basic thing in teaching English to kids is the knowledge to interest them, to involve them in the process, and the most exciting process for young children is the game. For a child, play is life.

We can say that games for learning English for children are the main form of learning a foreign language. They create a relaxed situation in which learning is easier compared to forced ways of teaching. During the game, children not only memorize new words, expressions or rules, but also develop

attention, memory, thinking and, of course, creativity. The use of games in teaching helps to maintain interest in the English language, and also helps to more easily assimilate, consolidate and master the lesson material.

The advantages of this method are that it helps to form a strong attachment between the teacher and the child, and also the stimulation of the senses helps the child to know his personality and grow up to be comprehensively developed, and also this method of extraordinary education brings up original-minded children.

Below are examples.

1. "Confusion" This game is useful in that it develops auditory orientation. The facilitator (teacher) names a part of the body while simultaneously touching another part of the body. I will give an example to make it clear, I said the word Eyes (eyes), but points to the ear. The task of children is to touch exactly that part of the body that he names, and does not indicate. In this way, actions can be studied, children must follow the voiced commands, and not the completed action. You can give the same example, the teacher said Clap your hands - clap your hands, and he stomps his feet, the players in this case should clap their hands.

2. "Step on color". The game is very exciting and at the same time very easy. To begin with, the teacher must prepare special templates from different colors of cardboard and cut them out in the form of a foot. After that, you can start playing. The host, that is, the teacher says "Step on red" - step on red, the player must step on the red foot. Children themselves can also become leaders. This game, of course, is best played in pairs. The second way is to order something. For example: we give the command "quickly touch something yellow" - quickly touch something yellow. You can also complicate the game a little, for example, give the command give me something - give me a green pen - give me a green pen. And this game is better to play in a group form, about five seven participants. The main task is to develop children's attention and memory, with the help of this

game it will be easier for children to remember the names of colors.

3. "Close the window". Children are given cards - panels with the image of objects or animals, birds and chips. Next, words are pronounced on a predetermined topic, the children must close the window of the card in which the named word is shown.

4. "Show". Children are given cards with the image of objects, animals, for example, poultry. The adult names the bird in English, the children raise cards with the image of the named bird.

5. "Touch". An adult offers a task: the children should come to the table and touch the toy that is called to him. Then the children play in pairs: one child asks to touch the toy, the other does. Then the children change places.

6. "Who am I?" first you need to prepare special cards that depict animals, birds, objects, etc. The teacher's task is to put these cards on the rounded belt that is on the head of the participants, so that everyone can see what kind of characters the others are, but not himself. The task of each player is to guess what character he is. To do this, he must ask questions that can only be answered with "yes" or "no".

A few sample questions:

Am I alive? Am I a vegetable? Am I an animal? Do I have legs? Could I be a pet? Can I be eaten? Can I fly? Do I make noise? Can I swim? Do I have hair? Am I red (blue, yellow, white.....)?

This game is very useful as it trains the ability to build interrogative sentences.

You can choose a different category of topics: for example, subjects: Is it big? Can you touch it? Can you see it in the classroom?

Using game methods for teaching children, these methods will form the ability to understand the simplest words and sentences, helps develop active speech faster, promotes the development of communication skills, trains memory, and also provides new sources of information about the world around.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In interactive games, children not only develop speech activity, assimilate and consolidate lexical and grammatical material, but also develop mental processes: thinking, memory, voluntary attention, as well as important personality traits such as purposefulness, concentration, the ability to subordinate one's behavior to certain rules and, of course, such social feelings as empathy, the ability to come to the rescue, collectivism, friendship.

The game frees children from the fear of speaking a foreign language, leaves a vivid impression of the lesson. To effectively solve this problem, optimal pedagogical conditions, features of interaction with children and families were determined:

- The organization of the educational process has been thought through through various types of children's activities: educational, playful, creative, contributing to the unification of the mental, emotional, and motor activities of children;
- An educational, subject-developing learning environment has been created;
- A system of long-term planning has been developed; abstracts of specially organized integrated, thematic classes with the definition of game material;
- Selected didactic games that correspond to the topics of the classes, carried out their classification into groups according to the types of children's speech activity.

An essential sign of the quality of education is the interaction with parents, active participants in the pedagogical process. We organize both general and individual consultations, seminars and workshops. We invite them to classes, parent meetings, holidays.

A childhood is a world of fairy tales, exciting games, stories and songs, where the interest to play with peers reigns. That's why:

- do not rush to deprive children of this joy;
- do not be afraid that children who play too much will not learn seriousness and responsibility.

The child is perfectly able to distinguish the fictional world from the real world and transfer the skills acquired in the game to real meaningful activities.

The game method of teaching is the most effective, as it allows you to accustom to mental work gradually. It makes the lesson creative and interesting.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, Games in English for children increase the motivation to learn the language in ordinary times, outside of the game. The process of the game itself is also suitable for learning, in such an environment information is understood better than in a lesson. This is joyful and useful in itself.

In short, this is the best way to teach English to preschool children. Thanks to the game, you can achieve unprecedented success in teaching children. The most elementary education, that is, preschool teaching of languages and other subjects, of course, should begin with game methods.

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